

THE MAIN ESSENCE OF FORMING COLLABORATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL APPROACHES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. Recently, in search of new approaches to teaching and upbringing modern schoolchildren in pedagogical research, scientists increasingly turn to the consideration of such a concept as strategy. This expands the research space and thus allows, on the one hand, to consider the types and technologies of teaching in the context of a certain strategy, and on the other hand, to develop new strategies for teaching and upbringing. The article is devoted to the consideration of the problem of organizing collaborative learning in a modern school as a new approach to teaching and upbringing students.

Keywords: collaborative learning, teaching strategy, collaboration, collaborative environment, educational potential.

INTRODUCTION

The strategy in teaching and education can be considered “as a general plan of joint actions of the teacher and the student, based on a forecast, determining the immediate prospects of his intellectual and personal development in the process of studying the subject chosen by him or any subject area, and including all aspects of the educational process” [1]. The strategy of teaching and education includes the development of the goal, the process of mastering the content of the training, support for students and feedback.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study is conducted on the basis of methods of theoretical analysis and generalization of the provisions of pedagogical science. For this purpose, theoretical provisions on the development of teaching strategies and the organization of collaborative learning as a strategy for learning in partnership are updated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Recently, in search of new approaches to teaching and educating modern schoolchildren, scientists in pedagogical research increasingly turn to the consideration of such a concept as strategy. This expands the research space and thus allows, on the one hand, to consider the types and technologies of teaching in the context of a certain strategy, and on the other hand, to develop new strategies for teaching and education.

The main principles of choosing strategies, researchers believe, are:

- active and self-directed learning;
- reliance on the life experience of the learner and research practice;
- focus on reflexivity;
- interactivity and cooperation in the educational process [2].

The proposed learning strategies are very diverse. For example, scientists named after A. I. Herzen [3] offer the following.

The strategy of self-directed learning is the purposeful development or strengthening of some personal quality. In this case, the person himself thinks through the process of self-development and its stages. This strategy is based on the activation of self-awareness, self-esteem, self-control, such personal qualities as initiative, optimism, self-confidence, etc. in the learning process. It is most often used in higher and postgraduate education.

The strategy of experimental learning is the acquisition of new information and practical skills based on the analysis of one's previous experience and the experience of other people. It is based on the activation of reflection. It is most often used in adult education.

Contextual learning strategy – learning through modeling the subject and social content of the activity.

Critical learning strategy. Promotes the formation of one's own opinion in the situation of searching for information, conscious and objective assessment of the information received, as well as changing one's views when identifying new information. Based on the ability to work critically with a large flow of information.

Communicative learning strategies. Model behavior for the dynamics of conversation and interaction in a group in a public communication situation. Used in the process of teaching foreign languages, in communication courses.

Strategies for learning in partnership: cooperative learning, collaborative learning, knowledge management, natural learning, learning in an online community.

Within the framework of this approach, collaborative learning refers to the strategy of learning in partnership.

Translated from English, collaborative means "common", "united", "joint". In pedagogical science, the term "collaboration" means "cooperation", "partnership". It implies a process of joint activity of people to achieve common goals, in which knowledge is exchanged, learning and agreement is reached. The definition of "collaborative learning" (learning in partnership) means a learning strategy that allows organizing group work of students to solve a problem, complete a task or create a product.

Collaborative learning is a social and emotional development of schoolchildren. This means that such personal qualities as respect, recognition of the abilities and personal contribution of each group member, the desire and ability to cooperate, and mutual understanding are formed [4].

Collaborative learning is based on a number of theories and concepts:

- 1) the concepts of knowledge management, knowledge conversion;
- 2) conceptual provisions of the pedagogy of cooperation;
- 3) ideas of collective, joint activity, collegiality;
- 4) provisions of the theory of communication, since communication in this learning strategy is the main tool for exchanging knowledge.

The educational value of collaborative learning is ensured by the ideas of the pedagogy of cooperation, which allow us to understand that in the educational process all subjects are united in common activities by relationships of camaraderie, mutual respect, mutual assistance, and collectivism. Cooperation involves taking into account the interests and desires of each person, support, gradual overcoming of disagreements, and concessions. This is the most productive form of behavior in a conflict management situation.

Cooperative learning has educational potential and promotes the formation of the ability and readiness for cooperation, conflict resolution, interaction with a team, partners. Students learn to organize joint activities based on the principles of cooperation and participate in them, understand their role as a partner. At the same time, they develop such personal qualities as tolerance for different points of view and types of behavior that differ from what they are used to, responsibility for the results of joint work, the ability to respect someone else's point of view, listen to a partner, conduct a business discussion, reach agreement in conflict situations and controversial issues is formed.

The productivity of joint learning is expressed in the following characteristics:

- positive interdependence: each student must fully participate in the work, have their own task for which they are responsible to others, understand that their achievements affect the effectiveness of the group;
- face-to-face interaction: assistance, promotion of each other's success;
- social skills: each student masters effective communication methods, interpersonal and group interaction skills;
- group assessment: the group must assess its effectiveness and develop ways to improve it [5].

Collaborative learning is learning in joint group activities. The technology of group work includes methods of collective learning known in Russian pedagogy.

Analysis of the results of pedagogical research allows us to talk about the possibility of collective activity for solving a number of pedagogical problems, such as socialization and education of the personality of students (development of the ability to work in a team, cooperate, lead and obey, perform various functions, etc.), development of cognitive interest, activity, independence, collectivist, communicative qualities of the individual, a responsible attitude to study, etc.

Communication theories, which reveal the essence of communicative action, the communicative process, are also of great importance for educational practice. Collaborative learning involves interpersonal communication. The success of solving educational problems depends on its correct organization.

CONCLUSION

The above characteristics of collaborative learning allow us to come to the conclusion that collaborative learning has great educational potential. By creating a collaborative environment in the learning process, we immerse schoolchildren in a common communicative context of activity, the main features of which are the collectivity of actions, the joint nature of group work, collegiality, co-authorship, partnership, interaction, and cooperation.

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